

REPORT

A.2.2.1: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for siloxanes and silicon

As part of WP2 task 2.2, BiometCAP partners have demonstrated the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in Task 2.1 (specifically in A2.1.4) using the following validated methods: gas chromatography, spectroscopy and spectrometry analytical systems. The validation exercise is shown on the map below:

IMBiH, NPL, VSL and RISE have each validated the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for total silicon using a range of different atomic/ionic emission spectrometry-based analysers and for individual siloxanes (siloxanes: L2, L3, D3, D4, D5) using thermal desorption gas chromatography mass spectrometry flame ionization detector (TD-GC/MS/FID) at VSL and RISE, and GC-IMS at NPL. RISE, IMBiH, VSL and NPL will use the gravimetrically prepared static standards produced in A1.1.2 and A1.1.3.

The four reports are gathered in this document.

Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for Atomic Emission Spectroscopy Analysis of Total Silicon in Biomethane

Task 2.2.1

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I. SUMMARY

This report was created to validate the fitness for purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4.

The report outlines the method for testing total silicon in biomethane and similar gas matrices. It details the analytical process for measuring total silicon content in the gas phase, which includes absorbing siloxane compounds in a mineral medium, derivatizing the siloxane into a suitable analytical form, and analysing it using an optical atomic plasma emission method. The method involves the development and optimization of the instrumental procedure, sampling, derivatization, sample preparation, and quality control.

The method underwent rigorous validation steps, assessing linearity, stability, robustness, selectivity,

sensitivity, and measurement uncertainty. These validations ensure the method's reliability and accuracy in detecting low levels of silicon ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ range) from prevalent siloxane compounds in biogas, such as L2, L3, D4, and D5.

II. INTRODUCTION

Biomethane, a renewable form of natural gas produced from organic materials, is increasingly recognized as a sustainable energy source. As its production and utilization grow, ensuring the purity and quality of biomethane becomes critically important. One key aspect of this quality control is the measurement of silicon content.

Silicon in biomethane typically originates from siloxanes, which are volatile silicon-containing compounds commonly found in biogas derived from sewage sludge, landfill waste, and certain agricultural residues. When biomethane is used as a fuel, these siloxanes can be problematic. Upon combustion, they form silica deposits that can damage engines, turbines, and other gas utilization equipment, leading to increased maintenance costs and operational downtimes. Moreover, silica deposits can adversely affect the efficiency and lifespan of energy conversion systems.

Accurate measurement of silicon in biomethane is essential to mitigate these risks. Reliable data on silicon content helps producers ensure their biomethane meets industry standards and regulatory requirements, thereby safeguarding equipment and maintaining operational efficiency. Moreover, accurate data supports the optimization of biogas cleaning processes, enhancing the overall sustainability and economic viability of biomethane production.

Quality data with established traceability is foundational to this effort. Traceability ensures that measurements are consistent, reproducible, and comparable over time and across different laboratories. It provides confidence that the analytical results are accurate and reliable, which is crucial for regulatory compliance and for making informed decisions regarding process control and quality assurance. Establishing traceability involves using standardized methods, calibrating instruments with certified reference materials, and following rigorous quality control protocols. This systematic approach not only enhances the credibility of the data but also supports continuous improvement in biomethane production processes.

In summary, the accurate measurement of silicon in biomethane is vital for maintaining equipment integrity, meeting quality standards, and supporting sustainable energy practices. Ensuring high-quality, traceable data underpins these efforts, providing a robust foundation for effective quality control and regulatory compliance in the biomethane industry.

Table 1: List of main siloxane compounds present in biogas

Linear siloxanes (abbreviation and full name)	Structural formula	MW	Cyclic siloxanes (abbreviation and full name)	Structural formula	MW

L2 Hexamethyldisiloxane		222.46			
L3 Octamethyltrisiloxane		296.62			
L4 Decamethyltetrasiloxane		370.77			
L5 Dodecamethylpentasiloxane		444.92			

III. MATERIAL AND METHODS OF WORK

3.1 Gas Flow Meter with Temperature Sensor for Measuring Biomethane Volume in Gas Bubbler Collection System

Accurate measurement of the volume of biomethane passing through a gas bubbler system is essential for precise quantification of silicon content. To achieve this, a gas flow meter equipped with a temperature sensor is utilized. This combination ensures accurate volume measurement by accounting for variations in temperature, which can affect gas flow rates and volumes.

A gas flow meter with an integrated temperature sensor is a critical component in the biomethane sampling process. It provides real-time measurement of gas flow rates and adjusts for temperature fluctuations, ensuring accurate and reliable data collection.

The gas flow meter provides precise measurement of the flow rate of biomethane passing through the bubbler system. Accurate flow measurement is essential for determining the volume of gas sampled and for calculating the concentration of silicon in the biomethane.

High-resolution sensors and digital displays enhance the accuracy and readability of flow measurements.

The integrated temperature sensor continuously monitors the temperature of the gas. Since gas volume is temperature-dependent, the sensor ensures that any variations in temperature are accounted for, providing corrected flow rate and volume measurements.

Temperature compensation is crucial for maintaining accuracy, especially in environments where temperature fluctuations are common.

The gas flow meter with temperature sensor allows for real-time monitoring and recording of flow rates and temperatures. This capability enables immediate adjustments and ensures that sampling conditions remain optimal throughout the process.

The combination of flow and temperature measurement ensures consistent and reliable data. This consistency is critical for reproducible silicon analysis and for maintaining the integrity of the sampling process.

Regular calibration and maintenance of the flow meter and temperature sensor enhance their reliability and accuracy over time.

3.1.1 Procedure for Using Gas Flow Meter with Temperature Sensor

The following steps outline the procedure for using a gas flow meter with an integrated temperature sensor in a gas bubbler collection system:

Setup:

Install the gas flow meter in the gas line between the biomethane source and the gas bubbler system. Ensure that the flow meter is securely connected and that there are no leaks in the setup.

Verify that the temperature sensor is correctly positioned to accurately measure the temperature of the gas flowing through the meter.

Calibration:

Calibrate the gas flow meter and temperature sensor according to the manufacturer's instructions. Calibration ensures that the measurements are accurate and traceable to recognized standards. Perform calibration checks periodically to maintain the accuracy and reliability of the instruments.

Sampling:

Begin the flow of biomethane through the gas flow meter and into the gas bubbler system. Adjust the flow rate using the flow controller to achieve the desired sampling conditions.

Monitor the flow rate and temperature in real-time using the digital display or connected data logging system. Ensure that the flow remains steady and within the optimal range for the duration of the sampling period.

Data Recording:

Record the flow rate and temperature data continuously or at regular intervals during the sampling process. Accurate data recording is essential for calculating the total volume of biomethane sampled and for subsequent silicon analysis.

Use the recorded data to correct for any temperature-induced variations in gas volume, ensuring that the reported volume is accurate.

Post-Sampling Analysis:

After completing the sampling, use the recorded flow and temperature data to calculate the total volume of biomethane that passed through the bubbler system.

Use this volume data, along with the silicon concentration measured in the collected solution, to determine the concentration of silicon in the biomethane sample.

In conclusion, the use of a gas flow meter with an integrated temperature sensor is essential for

accurate measurement of biomethane volume in gas bubbler collection systems. This setup ensures precise flow rate monitoring and temperature compensation, leading to reliable and accurate quantification of silicon in biomethane. Such precision supports robust quality control and regulatory compliance in biomethane production and utilization.

For the purpose of this study the following equipment was used:

- a) Gas flow meter with temperature sensor Aalborg DFM 26 S-TAL2-AA2

Figure 1 Gas flow meter

3.2 Gas Collection Using a Gas Bubbler System in Concentrated Nitric Acid

In the process of measuring silicon in biomethane, the collection of gas samples is a crucial step. One effective method for capturing silicon-containing compounds from biomethane is the use of a gas bubbler system containing concentrated nitric acid. This method ensures efficient trapping and subsequent analysis of silicon.

3.2.1 Gas Bubbler System

A gas bubbler system is designed to capture gaseous samples by bubbling them through a liquid medium. In the context of silicon analysis in biomethane, the liquid medium is typically concentrated nitric acid (HNO_3). This system allows for the efficient absorption and conversion of silicon compounds into a form that can be easily analysed.

Silicon-containing compounds, such as siloxanes present in biomethane, are effectively absorbed by the concentrated nitric acid as the gas bubbles through the solution.

Nitric acid reacts with these silicon compounds, converting them into soluble silicates or silicon dioxide, which remain in the acidic solution for subsequent analysis.

Concentrated nitric acid is a strong oxidizing agent, which helps in breaking down complex silicon compounds and ensuring their complete capture in the solution.

The acidic environment prevents the re-volatilization of silicon compounds, maintaining their presence in the liquid phase for accurate measurement.

Gas bubbler systems are relatively simple to set up and operate, making them suitable for routine sampling in laboratory and field settings.

Regular maintenance, such as cleaning and replenishing the acid solution, ensures consistent performance and reliability of the system.

3.2.2 Procedure for Gas Collection

The following steps outline the procedure for collecting biomethane samples using a gas bubbler system with concentrated nitric acid:

Setup:

Prepare the gas bubbler system by filling the bubbler with concentrated nitric acid to a specified level. Ensure that the acid is handled with appropriate safety precautions, including the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and fume hoods.

Connect the inlet of the bubbler to the biomethane gas source, ensuring a secure and leak-free connection. The outlet of the bubbler can be connected to an exhaust system or additional bubblers if needed.

Gas Flow Control:

Use a gas flow controller to regulate the flow rate of biomethane into the bubbler. The flow rate should be optimized to ensure efficient bubbling and maximum contact time between the gas and the acid solution.

Typical flow rates range from 50 to 500 mL/min, depending on the specific requirements of the analysis and the concentration of silicon compounds in the gas.

Sampling:

Allow the biomethane to bubble through the concentrated nitric acid for a predetermined period, ensuring sufficient time for the capture of silicon compounds. The duration of sampling can vary based on the expected silicon concentration and the volume of gas being analysed.

Monitor the gas flow and ensure that the bubbling is consistent and stable throughout the sampling period.

Post-Sampling Processing:

After the sampling period, disconnect the gas flow and carefully transfer the nitric acid solution containing the captured silicon compounds into a suitable container for analysis.

Rinse the bubbler with additional nitric acid or deionized water to ensure complete transfer of the silicon compounds into the analytical solution.

3.3 Atomic Emission Spectrometry

Atomic Emission Spectrometry (AES) is a powerful analytical technique used to determine the

concentration of elements in a sample by measuring the intensity of light emitted from excited atoms or ions. This technique leverages the unique emission spectra of elements, allowing for precise identification and quantification. In particular, Microwave Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (MPAES) has gained prominence due to its advantages in terms of cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and environmental impact.

3.3.1 Microwave Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometer (MPAES)

The MPAES is a specialized form of AES that uses microwave energy to produce a plasma source. The plasma, typically generated using nitrogen, provides a stable and robust environment for the excitation of sample atoms. This approach is particularly advantageous for analysing non-metals and metals, including silicon in complex matrices like biomethane.

The MPAES employs microwave energy to ionize nitrogen gas, creating a high-temperature plasma. This plasma serves as an excitation source, promoting the emission of characteristic wavelengths from the sample atoms.

Nitrogen is used due to its inert nature and availability, which ensures a consistent and contamination-free plasma environment. Additionally, nitrogen reduces operational costs compared to noble gases like argon.

For silicon analysis, specific emission lines are selected based on their intensity and interference-free nature. The choice of wavelengths is critical to ensure accurate quantification, with common wavelengths for silicon being around 251.6 nm and 288.1 nm. The instrument's monochromator isolates these emission lines, allowing for precise measurement of their intensity.

Plasma pressure and quality are carefully controlled to maintain optimal excitation conditions. The pressure is adjusted to achieve a balance between sufficient atomization and minimal background interference.

Parameters such as gas flow rates and microwave power are optimized to ensure a stable and homogeneous plasma. This stability is crucial for reproducible and accurate measurements.

Samples are typically introduced into the plasma through a nebulizer, which converts the liquid sample into a fine aerosol. The suction and nebulization parameters are optimized to maximize the efficiency of sample introduction and to ensure consistent aerosol formation.

Parameters such as the uptake rate, nebulizer gas flow, and spray chamber conditions are fine-tuned to achieve optimal aerosol generation and transport to the plasma.

3.3.2 Instrument Calibration and Quality Control

The MPAES is calibrated using standards of known silicon concentrations. This calibration establishes a relationship between emission intensity and silicon concentration.

Quality Control:

Regular checks using control samples and blanks ensure the instrument's performance remains consistent. Calibration verification and quality control samples are analysed periodically to monitor and maintain accuracy.

In summary, the MPAES, with its microwave-induced nitrogen plasma, provides a robust and efficient platform for silicon analysis in biomethane. By carefully selecting wavelengths, optimizing plasma conditions, and fine-tuning sample introduction parameters, the MPAES ensures accurate, precise, and reliable measurements. This makes it an invaluable tool in the quality control and assurance processes for biomethane production, supporting the industry's goals of sustainability and operational

efficiency.

3.4 Chemicals Used in the Analysis of Silicon in Biomethane

Accurate analysis of silicon in biomethane using Microwave Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (MPAES) requires the use of high-purity chemicals and standards. These chemicals ensure the reliability and accuracy of the measurements by minimizing contamination and providing consistent results. The following are key chemicals used in this analytical process:

- **Trace Metal Grade Nitric Acid**

Trace metal grade nitric acid (HNO_3) is used for the preparation and digestion of samples. Its high purity minimizes contamination from other metals, ensuring accurate silicon analysis.

In the gas bubbler system, concentrated nitric acid absorbs and converts silicon-containing compounds in biomethane into a soluble form, facilitating subsequent analysis.

Properties:

- **Pure Potassium Hydroxide (KOH)**

KOH solutions are used to neutralize acidic components in the sample matrix, aiding in the extraction and stabilization of silicon compounds.

- **Pure Hydrofluoric Acid (HF)**

Pure hydrofluoric acid is used to extract silicon from complex matrices, such as biomethane, by dissolving silicate minerals and other silicon-containing compounds.

HF is employed in the digestion process to break down solid samples and release silicon into a measurable form.

- **Siloxane Compounds**

Specific siloxane compounds, such as hexamethyldisiloxane (L2) or octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane (D4), are used to simulate silicon contamination in biomethane samples.

These compounds are used to validate the analytical method and ensure efficacy of derivatization process.

- **Traceable Silicon Standard Solution**

Silicon standard solutions, traceable to National Metrology Institutes, are used to produce calibration curve and as calibration control standard. This ensures the accuracy and traceability of the measurements.

Due to the reactive and potentially hazardous nature of these chemicals, proper handling and safety precautions are essential:

- **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):**

Use appropriate PPE, including gloves, goggles, and lab coats, when handling these chemicals.

Ventilation:

Conduct all procedures involving volatile or corrosive chemicals, such as nitric acid and hydrofluoric acid, in a fume hood to prevent exposure to harmful fumes.

Store chemicals in suitable containers, clearly labelled, and in accordance with safety guidelines to prevent accidental mixing or contamination.

Dispose of chemical wastes following regulatory requirements and best practices for hazardous waste management.

In conclusion, the use of high-purity chemicals, such as trace metal grade nitric acid, pure KOH, pure HF, siloxane compounds, and NIST-traceable silicon standard solutions, is essential for the accurate and reliable analysis of silicon in biomethane. These chemicals ensure minimal contamination, precise calibration, and consistent results, supporting robust analytical procedures and quality control in biomethane production and utilization.

For the purpose of sample preparation and calibration the following chemicals and auxiliary equipment was used:

Concentrated Nitric acid ultrapure grade, 69.0-70.0%, Sigma Aldrich;

Hydrogen peroxide, ultrapure, 30%

Potassium hydroxide pellets

Concentrated fluoric acid, ultrapure, 48%

Pure siloxane compounds:

Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane (D4) 100 %/Merck;

Hexamethyldisiloxane (L2) 99,6 %+/Acros Organics;

Si standard solution, (1000 mg/L) Supelco Certified Reference Standard traceable to NIST SRM 3150;

Laboratory plasticware; hotplate

Micropipettes – various volumes

Analytical balance, Sartorius MSE225S-OCE-DU

IV. VALIDATION PARAMETERS

4.1 Method flowchart

A flowchart of the analytical method outlines the step-by-step process of sample preparation, conducting an analysis in order to ensure systematic and reproducible results.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the optimized method

4.2 Method stability – robustness and selectivity

The stability and selectivity of the Atomic Emission Spectrometry (AES) method for silicon analysis in a matrix containing HNO₃, KOH, and HF has been demonstrated by:

Matrix Considerations:

The presence of HNO₃, KOH, and HF can affect the stability and accuracy of the AES measurements due to potential matrix effects. This was checked by using various quality control samples such as calibration and sample blanks, calibration and sample derivatization controls.

Instrument Calibration:

Instrument calibration is done regularly, for each set of samples using traceable standards that closely match the sample matrix.

Interference Management:

Background correction is utilized to address any spectral interferences caused by the matrix components. Having in mind the nature and source of the sample, absence of other, possibly interfering elements is expected and confirmed by analysis.

Figure 2: Possible spectral interferences for silicon at selected analytical line

Stated elements are not present in the sample providing selectivity of the instrumental setting. Blank measurements - reagents and water - proved no contamination with silicon from outside sources.

Matrix-matched calibration standards to mitigate matrix effects are used.

Repeatability and reproducibility:

All individual analyses are conducted in at least 7 replicates with %RSD<3 to prove repeatability. Reproducibility was conducted as replicate measurements of the same sample from several calibration curves and calculated by means of pooled standard deviation, also used for assessing method precision.

Quality control measures, such as analysing standard reference materials and control samples are regularly implemented.

Maintenance and Monitoring:

The instrument analytical parts – sample introduction system and plasma torch have been regularly maintained and cleaned to prevent contamination and ensure consistent performance.

Stability of the emission signal is monitored over time and analytical parameters are adjusted as needed.

4.3 Method linearity and uncertainty of calibration curve

The linearity of an analytical method refers to its ability to provide results that are directly proportional to the concentration of an analyte in a sample over a specified range. In practical terms, this means that as the concentration of the analyte increases the measured response (e.g., signal intensity) changes proportionally. Linearity is typically assessed by plotting calibration curves and evaluating correlation coefficients, ensuring that the method accurately measures analyte concentrations across its intended range without significant deviation from linearity. Figures 3 and 4 also show linear equation and correlation coefficient related to each calibration curve. Correlation coefficient is close to 1 (condition set $r^2 > 0,995$), thus indicates a strong linear correlation between the measured response and analyte concentration.

Figures 3 and 4: Examples of used calibration curves and emission peaks for silicon at selected analytical line

Figures 5 and 6 show residual plots obtained from data for the two calibration curves showed above. It is assumed that any error in the data lies solely in y values, thus the best-fit straight line shown in the figures is termed "Line of regression of y on x". During method validation, the absence of a trend in the regression line confirms the method's ability to provide reliable and reproducible results

Figures 5 and 6: Residual plots

Uncertainty from calibration curves were calculated as:

<p>UNCERTAINTY FROM LINEAR CALIBRATION</p> $u_{cal} = \frac{s_{y,x}}{a} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{c_{samp}}} + \frac{1}{n_{c_i}} + \frac{(\bar{c}_{samp} - \bar{c})^2}{\sum(c_i - \bar{c})^2}}$ <p>QUAM:2012, Example A5; page 77</p>	<p>RESIDUAL STANDARD DEVIATION</p> $s_{y,x} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum[y_i - (b + a * c_i)]^2}{n - 2}}$ <p>QUAM:2012, Example A5; page 78</p>
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Cal. Curve 1 y(intensity)= a*x(Ci) +b	b (intercept)	4,5628
	a (slope)	6.739,3460

<i>calibration curve 1 data</i>				
	<i>experimental conc.</i>	<i>predicted conc.</i>	<i>experimental intensity</i>	<i>predicted intensity</i>
n	(<i>c_i</i>)	(<i>c'</i>)	(<i>y_i</i>)	(<i>y'</i>)
1	0,0483	0,0465	330,0361	318,1369
2	0,0939	0,0936	637,4785	635,6800
3	0,1799	0,1863	1216,9678	1260,2851
4	0,3805	0,3822	2569,1371	2580,4443
5	0,5646	0,5659	3809,8939	3818,6178
6	0,7626	0,7611	5144,2475	5134,1919
7	0,9492	0,9421	6401,5815	6354,0198

S_{y,x} =	30,293
U_{cal}	0,00241 mg/kg

Cal. Curve 2 y(intensity)= a*x(Ci) +b	b (intercept)	10,9900
	a (slope)	8.266,2348

<i>calibration curve 2 data</i>				
	<i>experimental conc.</i>	<i>predicted conc.</i>	<i>experimental intensity</i>	<i>predicted intensity</i>
n	(<i>c_i</i>)	(<i>c'</i>)	(<i>y_i</i>)	(<i>y'</i>)

1	0,0507	0,0465	430,0135	395,6085
2	0,0935	0,0936	783,5610	785,0952
3	0,1816	0,1863	1512,1460	1551,2129
4	0,3825	0,3822	3172,8836	3170,4719
5	0,5706	0,5659	4727,4750	4689,1701
6	0,7598	0,7611	6291,4211	6302,8051
7	0,9389	0,9421	7771,7914	7799,0012

$S_{y,x} =$	31,797
u_{cal}	0,00207 mg/kg

4.4 Method sensitivity – limits of detection and quantification

The sensitivity of an analytical method refers to its ability to reliably detect and quantify low concentrations of analytes in a sample. Sensitivity is influenced by various factors including the sample matrix, concentration range, sensitivity of detection system, analytical line selected, etc. Optimization of these factors is essential to enhance sensitivity and improve the method's performance. Sensitivity of the method is commonly assessed by determining limits of detection (LOD) and limits of quantification (LOQ).

LOD is the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be reliably distinguished from the background noise of the measurement system. LOD is typically determined as the concentration at which the signal-to-noise ratio reaches a defined value.

For the validation purposes, LOD was assessed by measuring sample near to LOD concentration in 10 replicates and LOD was calculated by multiplying pooled standard deviation of two sets of 10 measurements with 3.

LOQ is the lowest concentration of an analyte that can be quantified with acceptable accuracy and precision. LOQ is crucial for ensuring that analyte concentrations can be accurately determined rather than just detected. For the validation purposes LOQ was calculated by multiplying pooled standard deviation of two sets of 10 measurements with 10. The results LOD and LOQ are given below.

Table 2: LOD and LOQ calculation

Table 3: Precision calculation

No. of replicates	Results for the 0,4 (mg/kg)			
1	0.3784	0.3790	0.3802	0.3776
2	0.3715	0.3797	0.3793	0.3648
3	0.3606	0.3816	0.3753	0.3712
4	0.3680	0.3717	0.3788	0.3788
5	0.3912	0.3870	0.3701	0.382
6	0.3822	0.3899	0.3662	0.3779
7	0.3869	0.3928	0.3607	0.3713
average	0.3770	0.3831	0.3729	0.3748
SD	0.0109	0.0073	0.0075	0.0059
v	1.1814E-04	5.2687E-05	5.6063E-05	3.5083E-05
S_{pooled}	0.0081			mg/kg
$S_{pooled} = \sqrt{\frac{(n_1 - 1)s_1^2 + (n_2 - 1)s_2^2 + \dots + (n_k - 1)s_k^2}{n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_k - k}}$				

variance check by F test	
F_{exo}	3,3675
F_{crit} (two tailed $\alpha=0,1$)	4,2839

4.6 Assessment of derivatization efficacy

Derivatization efficacy assessment for total silicone measurement involved evaluating the recovery data of total silicone measurement from siloxane compounds subjected to derivatization.

Selected siloxane compounds (L2 and D4) were derivatized according to specified procedure to form more stable or detectable derivative of silicon, namely SiF_6^{2-} anion that is stable in acidic media (2% nitric acid). The derivatized samples were analyzed by means of described AES method.

Recovery is calculated by comparing the measured concentration of total silicone from derivatized siloxanes to the predicted calculated concentration assuming 100% derivatization efficacy. Recovery data are given below in figures 7 and 8. It is proved that derivatization process is optimized and quantitative.

13.6. (readings of derivatized samples from 07.06.)	L2 experimental conc. (mg/kg)	L2 predicted conc. (mg/kg)	Recovery	R%
data set 1	0.1890	0.2230	0.8475	84.7547
	0.2077	0.2230	0.9314	93.1405
	0.2698	0.2230	1.2099	120.9885
	0.2324	0.2230	1.0422	104.2169
	0.2500	0.2230	1.1211	112.1094
	0.3045	0.2230	1.3655	136.5493
SD of exp. concentrations	0.0420		average R%	108.6265
19.6. (readings of derivatized samples from 13.06.)	L2 experimental conc	L2 predicted conc.	Recovery	R%
data set 2	0.2084	0.2239	0.9307	93.0721
	0.2181	0.2239	0.9740	97.4042
	0.2181	0.2239	0.9740	97.4042
SD of exp. concentrations	0.0056		average R%	95.9602
data set 3	0.2134	0.2239	0.9531	95.3052
	0.2093	0.2239	0.9347	93.4741
	0.2112	0.2239	0.9432	94.3226
SD of exp. concentrations	0.0021		average R%	94.3673
Weighted average recovery (%) for L2				101.90

13.6. (readings of derivatized samples from 07.06.)	D4 experimental conc. (mg/kg)	D4 predicted conc. (mg/kg)	Recovery	R%
data set 1	0.2751	0.2669	1.0308	103.0767
	0.2503	0.2669	0.9378	93.7845
	0.2673	0.2669	1.0015	100.1542
	0.3149	0.2669	1.1799	117.9893
	0.2617	0.2669	0.9806	98.0559
	0.2768	0.2669	1.0371	103.7137
SD of exp. concentrations	0.0221		average R%	102.7957
19.6. (readings of derivatized samples from 13.06.)	D4 experimental conc.	D4 predicted conc.	Recovery	R%
data set 2	0.2619	0.2768	0.9460	94.6031
	0.2666	0.2768	0.9630	96.3008
SD of exp. concentrations	0.0033		average R%	95.4520
data set 3	0.2527	0.2768	0.9128	91.2799
	0.2668	0.2768	0.9637	96.3731
SD of exp. concentrations	0.0100		average R%	93.8265
Weighted average recovery (%) for D4				99.53

Figures 7 and 8: Recovery data for Si from siloxanes

4.7 Estimation of bias

Sampling from the gas phase was done using reference gas mixture NPL ID A623 containing the following components and concentrations:

Component	Amount fraction (mg/m ³)	Amount fraction (μmol/mol)
L2	0.125	0.054
L3	0.125	0.036
D4	0.125	0.027
D5	0.125	0.021

This mixture corresponds with the overall silicon content of 0.500 mg/m³ ± 0,08 mg/m³.

Bias was estimated as:

$$u_{bias} = \sqrt{u_{\bar{x}}^2 + u_{ref}^2}$$

Where:

$$u_{\bar{x}} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$$

u_{ref} – combined measurement uncertainty of silicon concentration in gas mixture

Table 4: Data on silicon measurement from reference gas mixture

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Sample/Parameter	(NPL A623) Silicon content 0.5 mg/m³ ±0,08 mg/m³	(NPL A623) Silicon content 0.5 mg/m³ ±0,08 mg/m³	(NPL A623) Silicon content 0.5 mg/m³ ±0,08 mg/m³
Volume collected (at ambient pressure)	4,360 dm ³	5,368 dm ³	4,010 dm ³
Dilution factor	2	2	2
Calculated Si mass fraction assuming 100% efficiency	0,0201 mg/kg	0,0139 mg/kg	0,0124 mg/kg
Read Si mass fraction	0,0211 mg/kg	0,0134 mg/kg	0,0125 mg/kg
Read Si concentration in mg/m³	0,53	0,48	0,51
Efficiency - recovery	105%	96%	101%

Linearity as squared correlation coefficient r^2	0,9964	0,9987	0,9974
Standard deviation of measurements (7 replicates)	0,0007 mg/kg	0,0005 mg/kg	0,0005 mg/kg

Conversion of measurement uncertainty given in mg/m³ to mg/kg of solution:

In approximately 5 dm³ of gas mixture = ±0,0004 mg of silicon (from measurement uncertainty)

Gas mixture was captured in approximately 100g of solution to be measured, thus 1 kg of solution contains ±0,0040 mg of Si.

$$u_{bias} = \sqrt{0,0005^2 + 0,0040^2}$$

$$u_{bias} = 0,00404 \frac{mg}{kg} Si$$

4.8 Estimation of measurement uncertainty

Combined measurement uncertainty was assessed by empirical approach upon identification of uncertainty sources as square root of sum of squared quantities of individual sources given in concentration units for silicon measurement.

$$u_c = \sqrt{u_{prec}^2 + u_{bias\ gas}^2 + u_{cal\ curve}^2 + u_{Si\ standard}^2}$$

Where:

u_{prec} – pooled standard deviation of silicon measurements under reproducibility conditions

$u_{bias\ gas}$ – bias from silicon measurement using certified gas mixture

$u_{cal\ curve}$ – uncertainty of calibration

$u_{Si\ standard}$ – uncertainty of certified Si solution used for calibration standards

Expanded measurement uncertainty is calculated by multiplying the combined measurement uncertainty with coverage factor $k=2$.

Measurement uncertainty budget		
Individual uncertainties	u	unit
u_{prec}	0,0081	mg/kg of Si
$u_{bias\ gas}$	0,0040	mg/kg of Si
$u_{cal\ curve}$	0,0024	mg/kg of Si
$u_{Si\ standard}$	0,0015	mg/kg of Si
Combined measurement uncertainty	0,0095	mg/kg of Si

Expanded measurement uncertainty	0,0190	mg/kg of Si
Relative expanded measurement uncertainty	1,9	%

REPORT

A2.2.1: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for total silicon and for individual siloxanes using GC-IMS

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1: Introduction

The EURAMET project “BiometCAP” aims to develop a performance assessment protocol for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. This report describes the validation of the analytical method for determining the amount fraction of total silicon and individual siloxanes, namely L2 (hexamethyldisiloxane), L3 (octamethyltrisiloxane), D3 (hexamethylcyclotrisiloxane), D4 (octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane), and D5 (decamethylcyclopentasiloxane) siloxane in samples of synthetic biomethane, using GC-IMS, according to the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4.

The methods were validated using both static and dynamic reference standards. The static standards used were prepared gravimetrically and validated against NPL primary reference materials (NPL PRMs). The dynamic standards were produced using a thermal mass flow controller system, referred to herein as the “MFC dynamic system”. The dynamic standards were generated by diluting a previously validated static standard (2952) with N6.0 purity grade methane gas, using the MFC dynamic system with calculated blend ratios to achieve the desired amount fractions. The dynamic system was validated using a static “check standard” (9300).

The following performance criteria were evaluated as part of this report:

- Linearity;
- Selectivity;
- Trueness;
- Precision; and
- Limit-of-detection.

The general procedure for evaluating the performance of each analytical method is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 – Overview of performance evaluation process.

Step	Phase	Description	Plan	
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	L2, L3, D3, D4 and D5 siloxanes will be measured at 0.4 – 1.12 mg m ⁻³ total silicon. The criteria and target levels are:	
			Criterion	Target value
			Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	< 8.00
			Repeatability u_r (%)	< 8.00
			Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	< 8.00
		Expanded uncertainty U (%)	< 8.00	
2	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Gravimetric composition and uncertainties calculated using NPL software GravCalc2.	
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Two standards (9300, D223101), and two interference standards (D148949, D223095)	

4	Experimental	Perform a multi-point calibration experiment by collecting instrument response data for measurements of the reference gas mixtures designed and produced in accordance with step 4. The entire experiment should be conducted within a time period equivalent to that between routine calibrations.	One static standard (D223101) is repeated 5x to evaluate trueness. One static standard is measured 10x over three days to evaluate precision.
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2: Analytical Method

Dynamic gas standards were generated using the MFC dynamic system which was connected to the GC-IMS via a SilcoNert® 2000 coated stainless steel tubing, with a bypass system to achieve a consistent flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹ for all measurements (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1 – MFC dynamic dilution system used in this study.

Analysis was carried out using a GC-IMS-SILOX™ analyser manufactured by G.A.S Dortmund (*Figure 2*). The instrument uses an electrometer to determine the amount fraction of individual siloxanes and total silicon within a sample. The instrument is loaded with custom firmware (GC-IMS-SILOX™ version 4.08) which automatically quantifies the amount of siloxanes in a sample based on the manufacturer's calibration.

Figure 2 - GC-IMS-SILOX™ analyser.

The GC-IMS is a two-dimensional analytical technique, wherein the analytes are first separated using a GC capillary column (*T2* in Figure 3) using standard GC conditions. After eluting from the column, the components are transferred to a drift tube (*T1* in Figure 3) and ionised by a beta-radiation source. Inside the drift tube, the ionised analytes are subjected to an electrical field, causing the ions to move against the flow of carrier gas with a characteristic “drift time” based on their molecular weight and geometry. The ions are finally quantified by an electrometer at the end of the drift tube. In both the capillary column and the drift tube, the carrier gas is high purity nitrogen which has been dried by passing through a 200 mL 5 Å molecular sieve. An internal pump runs continuously to pull the sample through the loop and to purge the system.

Figure 3 – GC-IMS device plan from the instrument manual.

A full calibration of the instrument was performed by the manufacturer G.A.S Dortmund, with the calibration ranges as provided in Table 2.

Table 2- Manufacturer provided calibration ranges for the GC-IMS-SILOX instrument.

Component	Calibration range (mg m ⁻³)
L2 siloxane	0.03-2.5
L3 siloxane	0.03-4.0
D3 siloxane	0.03-3.0
D4 siloxane	0.03-3.0
D5 siloxane	0.1-3.0

At the beginning of each day, prior to measurement, the device was calibrated using the firmware's one-point calibration function against a previously validated NPL PRM 9311-R1 (Table 3). The results of the one-point calibration are shown in Appendix 1.

Table 3 – Gravimetric composition of siloxane PRM 9311-R1 used for one-point calibration of the GC-IMS.

Component	Gravimetric amount fraction (mg m ⁻³)	Gravimetric uncertainty (%)
L2 siloxane	2.234	0.323
L3 siloxane	2.232	0.322
D3 siloxane	1.983	0.362
D4 siloxane	2.068	0.348
D5 siloxane	2.158	0.335
Hexane	15.262	0.095
Methane	Balance	-

All measurements were conducted using the pre-loaded 58-minute measurement method in the instrument's firmware. This method has been designed to separate and quantify L2, L3, L4, L5 and D3, D4, D5, and D6 siloxanes using the parameters described in Table 4.

Table 4– GC-IMS default method parameters.

Parameter	Description
Sample loop volume	1 mL
GC column	MXT5 column (5% diphenyl, 95% dimethyl polysiloxane) 30 m x 0.32 mm x 1 µm
Column temperature	80°C
Carrier gas flow rate	5-15 mL min ⁻¹
Ion source	Tritium (300 MBq)
Drift tube length	53 mm
Drift tube voltage	2132 V
Drift tube temperature	65°C
Drift tube carrier flow rate	75 mL min ⁻¹
Method run time	58 minutes
Analytes measured	L2, L3, D3, D4, and D5 siloxanes (can measure L4, L5 and D6)

Gas standards were connected to the analyser using siliconert® 2000 coated stainless steel tubing connected to a T-junction bypass, as described in the instrument manual and shown in Figure 4. A flow meter was connected downstream of the bypass to verify that the sample reached the required minimum flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹ before each measurement.

Figure 4 – Schematic of sample inlet bypass configuration from the GC-IMS instrument manual.

For the determination of trueness and precision and the subsequent uncertainty budget, the amount fractions generated by the firmware’s quantification were used.

3: Reference Standards

A series of PRMs were prepared by NPL (Table 5) in accordance with ISO 6142-1ⁱⁱⁱ and validated using a direct comparison method based on ISO 6142^{iv}. Previously developed GC-FID and GC-MS techniques were used for the validations. The PRMs were prepared in ten litre Air Liquide “Megalife” passivated cylinders. For standards including D3 siloxane (9311-R1, D223101, 2952), n-hexane was used to dissolve the solid D3 siloxane. The resulting compositions are aligned with the requirements of EN 16723-1, which specifies that biomethane shall contain less than 0.5 mg m⁻³ of total silicon.

Table 5 – Gravimetric composition of NPL PRMs used in this study.

Component	Amount fraction (mg m ⁻³)			
	2952	9300	D223101	9311-R1
L2 siloxane	20.301	0.371	2.369	2.234
L3 siloxane	19.942	0.393	2.198	2.232
D3 siloxane	17.520	-	2.011	1.983
D4 siloxane	7.164	0.333	2.122	2.068
D5 siloxane	8.888	0.355	2.106	2.158
Hexane	135.399	-	15.480	15.262
Methane	Balance	Balance	Balance	Balance
Total silicon	26.840	0.468	3.936	3.919

4. Linearity

The linearity of the method was assessed by diluting a previously validated reference standard (2952) with N6.0 grade methane using the MFC dynamic dilution system developed by NPL. The calibration curves were generated using Microsoft Excel. Due to the experimental limitations of the analytical method (one hour run time), a single measurement was carried out for each point, spanning the amount fraction ranges given in Table 6. All the measurements were carried out in sequence over a seven-hour period.

Table 6 – Calculated amount fractions of siloxanes and total silicon generated by diluting standard 2952 with N6.0 purity grade methane.

Dilution factor	Amount fraction (mg m ⁻³)					
	L2 Siloxane	L3 Siloxane	D3 Siloxane	D4 Siloxane	D5 Siloxane	Total Si
25	0.812	0.798	0.701	0.287	0.356	1.074
32	0.634	0.623	0.547	0.224	0.278	0.839
45	0.451	0.443	0.389	0.159	0.451	0.692
75	0.271	0.266	0.234	0.096	0.271	0.416

As the GC-IMS is a two-dimensional analytical technique, measuring both drift time and retention time, analysis can be performed using either the integrated peak height or the integrated peak volume for each signal. For the linearity check, the chromatograms were manually processed using the manufacturer’s software “VOCal”. Analyte peaks were identified as two-dimensional “bins” as shown in Figure 5, based on the ranges specified in the instrument calibration, shown in Appendix 2.

Figure 5 – GC-IMS chromatogram of 2952. The orange labelled boxes display the expected retention time x drift time for each of the siloxanes measured.

The calibration curves for each siloxane are displayed in Figures 6-10, showing the correlation between amount fraction, peak height, and peak volume.

Figure 6 – Correlation between L2 amount fraction and peak height (left) and peak volume (right). Blue points represent calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, orange points represent static check standards, and the blue dotted line represents regression line.

Figure 7 – Correlation between L3 amount fraction and peak height (left) and peak volume (right). Blue points represent calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, orange points represent static check standards, and the blue dotted line represents regression line.

Figure 8 - Correlation between D3 amount fraction and peak height (left) and peak volume (right). Blue points represent calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, orange points represent static check standards, and the blue dotted line represents regression line.

Figure 9 - Correlation between D4 amount fraction and peak height (left) and peak volume (right). Blue points represent calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, orange points represent static check standards, and the blue dotted line represents regression line.

Figure 10 - Correlation between D5 amount fraction and peak height (left) and peak volume (right). Blue points represent calibration points from the MFC dynamic dilution system, orange points represent static check standards, and the blue dotted line represents regression line.

Each of the five siloxanes are shown to exhibit a linear correlation with peak height and peak volume over the amount fraction ranges studied. The correlation coefficients are >0.9, indicating that the linear equations fit the data well.

5. Trueness

The amount fractions of each siloxane in the instrument generated reports were compared to the gravimetric values of the static PRMs used (Table 4). The trueness was then evaluated as the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the gravimetric value using Equation 1.

$$\Delta_m = |c_m - c_{ref}| \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where:

Δ_m = the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value;

c_m = the mean measured value; and

c_{ref} = the gravimetric standard reference value.

The expanded uncertainty of the difference was determined by the quadrature sum of the uncertainties of the reference value and the measurement results according to Equation 2.

$$U_\Delta = 2 \sqrt{u_m^2 + u_{ref}^2} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where:

U_Δ = the expanded uncertainty of the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value ($k = 2$);

u_m = the uncertainty of the mean measured value ($k = 1$); and

u_{ref} = the uncertainty of the reference value ($k = 1$).

The expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainty corresponds to a confidence interval of 95%.

The following table provides an overview of the trueness of the instrument generated amount fractions of each siloxane, and total silicon, as measured against the static reference standard D223101, where the calculated amount fraction is an average of 5 repeated measurements.

If the expanded uncertainty of the difference is inferior to the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value, the difference is considered significant.

Table 6 – Summary of trueness analysis using NPL PRM D223101.

D223101	L2 Siloxane	L3 Siloxane	D3 Siloxane	D4 Siloxane	D5 Siloxane	Total Si
Gravimetric amount fraction (mg m ⁻³)	2.369	2.198	2.011	2.122	2.106	3.931
Relative gravimetric uncertainty (%)	0.303	0.325	0.355	0.337	0.355	0.150
Mean measured amount fraction (mg m ⁻³)	2.378	2.118	2.042	2.123	2.050	3.945
Relative standard deviation of the measured amount fraction (%)	1.432	2.921	1.618	2.534	5.703	1.857
Relative difference (%)	0.359	-3.662	1.566	0.024	1.687	0.343
Relative trueness uncertainty (%)	2.926	5.878	3.312	5.112	11.425	3.726

As the relative difference for each component is lower than the trueness uncertainty, this indicates that the performance of the instrument is suitable for this analysis. The trueness uncertainty is noticeably large for the D5 siloxane component; this is due to the large standard deviation of the measured amount fraction for this component, which could be caused by sample absorption within the sampling lines. Similarly, L3 siloxane is shown to exhibit a larger analytical bias compared to the other siloxanes, with the calculated amount being lower than the gravimetric amount fraction.

6. Precision

Measurement precision was split into repeatability and intermediate precision to distinguish the uncertainty contribution linked to the instrument (repeatability) and the uncertainty contribution due to day-to-day effects (intermediate precision).

The repeatability of the measurement method was determined by seven repeat measurements of the check standard (9300) over three days. At least three measurements were performed on each day under repeatability conditions (same operator, same instrument, same procedure). The amount fractions for total silicon and individual siloxanes calculated by the instrument's firmware were used for the analysis.

The results (Table 7) were processed using Excel's one-way ANOVA function to determine the repeatability (U_r) and intermediate precision (U_{day}).

Table 7- Repeatability and intermediate precision analysis of standard 9300.

	L2 Siloxane	L3 Siloxane	D4 Siloxane	D5 Siloxane	Total Si
Repeatability U_r (%)	1.234	0.366	1.608	1.282	0.538
Intermediate precision U_{day} (%)	3.096	1.565	2.246	2.410	1.443

7. Selectivity

NPL PRMs prepared and validated in WP1 were used to evaluate potential interferences from components likely to be present within biomethane and biogas (Table 9). The interferent PRMs were run using the same instrument configuration and method as for the other mixtures,

Table 9 – Gravimetric composition of NPL PRMs used for selectivity testing.

Component	Amount fraction ($\mu\text{mol/mol}$)	
	D148949	D223086
H2S	6.099	-
EtMeS	3.060	-
Et2S	3.054	-
MeSH	3.050	-
α -pinene	-	3.320
d-limonene	-	3.181
3-carene	-	3.00
Benzene	-	10
Toluene	-	10
L2 siloxane	-	0.085
L3 siloxane	-	0.056
D3 siloxane	-	0.056
D4 siloxane	-	0.042
D5 siloxane	-	0.033
Hexane	-	1.071
Methane	Balance	Balance

Inspection of the chromatograms (Figures 5 & 6) showed no regions of overlap between the interferent compounds and the siloxanes, as indicated by the orange dotted bins. The instrument generated reports stated "not detected" for all siloxanes after running D148949, confirming the absence of interference from these compounds.

Figure 5 – GC-IMS chromatogram of a sulphur odourant PRM, **D148949**. The orange labelled boxes display the expected retention time x drift time region for each of the siloxanes, indicating no overlap with the interferents H₂S, Et₂S, EtMeS, and MeSH.

Figure 6 – GC-IMS chromatogram of a synthetic biomethane PRM, **D223086**. The orange labelled boxes display the expected retention time x drift time region for each of the siloxanes, indicating no overlap with the interferences benzene, toluene, pinene, limonene, and carene.

8. Limit-of-detection

The limit of quantification (LOQ) is the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently determined using an analytical method, whereas the limit of detection refers to the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently detected. The LOQ and LODs for the described analytical methods were evaluated using the signal-to-noise approach, wherein the signal height of a low amount fraction sample is compared to a blank measurement. A signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1 is considered acceptable for evaluating the LOQ, and a ratio of 3 is acceptable for evaluating the LOD, as described in Equation 3.

$$LOQ/LOD = x \left(\frac{S}{N} \right) C \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

Where:

x = 3 when determining LOD;

S = signal height;

N = noise height; and

C = gravimetric amount fraction of the component.

The LOD analysis was carried out by diluting standard 2952 to a low amount fraction and comparing the peak heights to a blank run. The value for total silicon was estimated based on the LOD for D5 siloxane, as this had the highest value of the siloxanes studied. The results are summarised in Table 10.

Table 10 – Limit-of-detection analysis for siloxanes and total Si based on dilution of standard 2952.

Criterion	L2 Siloxane	L3 Siloxane	D4 Siloxane	D5 Siloxane	Total Si (based on D5)
Manufacturer's LOD	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.1	0.04
Calculated LOD	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.12	0.05

The value for total silicon meets the lower threshold requirements within both parts of EN 16723 (< 0.3 to 1 mgSi m⁻³).

9. Uncertainty budget

The uncertainty budget for each analytical method was calculated according to Equation 4.

$$U = k \sqrt{u_r^2 + u_{day}^2 + \Delta_m^2} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where:

U = the expanded uncertainty of the analytical method;

k = the coverage factor ($k = 2$ for 95% confidence level);

u_r = the relative uncertainty due to measurement repeatability;

u_{day} = the relative uncertainty due to day-to-day variations (within-lab reproducibility); and

Δ_m = the bias of the analytical method.

The expanded uncertainties for each of the five siloxanes analysed, and total silicon in biomethane, is presented in Table 10. As noted in Section 6, D3 siloxane was not included in the precision analysis.

Table 10 – summary of uncertainty budget for analysis of siloxanes and total Si in biomethane using GC-IMS

	L2 Siloxane	L3 Siloxane	D3 Siloxane	D4 Siloxane	D5 Siloxane	Total Si
Repeatability u_r (%)	1.23	0.366	-	1.608	1.282	0.538
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	3.096	1.565	-	2.246	2.410	1.443
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	0.3588	-3.662	1.566	0.024	1.687	0.343
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	6.70	8.00	-	5.525	6.42	3.15

Expanded uncertainties of less than 8% are considered acceptable for the analysis of siloxanes in biomethane.

10. Conclusion

The performance evaluation criteria for the validation of the analytical method using GC-IMS for the quantification of siloxanes and total silicon in biomethane is summarised in Table 11.

Table 11 – summary of performance criteria for analysis of siloxanes and total silicon in biomethane using GC-IMS.

Criterion	Target value	L2 Siloxane	L3 Siloxane	D4 Siloxane	D5 Siloxane	Total Si
LOD (mg m ⁻³)	<0.5	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.12	0.05
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	< 8.00	0.3588	-3.662	0.024	1.687	0.343
Repeatability u_r (%)	< 8.00	1.23	0.366	1.608	1.282	0.538
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	< 8.00	3.096	1.565	2.246	2.410	1.443
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	< 8.00	6.70	8.00	5.525	6.42	3.15

The validation of the method was performed according to the performance assessment protocol written in A2.1.4. This method covers the scope of ISO 2613-2:2023. The method described herein is therefore valid to the above-described acceptance criteria.

1. Appendix

Figure A1 – One-point calibration results against NPL PRM 9311-R1.

Figure A2 – chromatogram from manufacturer’s internal calibration with siloxane standards showing retention times.

REPORT

A.2.2.1: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for siloxanes with GC-FID at VSL.

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2. Introduction

The BiometCAP project has developed a performance assessment protocol for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment [1]. Here, this performance assessment protocol was validated for different siloxanes (Table 1). A gas chromatography with flame ionisation detector (GC-FID) was used as instrument. The validation parameters evaluated here were limit of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

Table 1: Overview of siloxanes used

Compound name	Abbreviation	Molecular formula
Hexamethyldisiloxane	L2	C ₆ H ₁₈ OSi ₂
Octamethyltrisiloxane	L3	C ₈ H ₂₄ O ₂ Si ₃
Hexamethylcyclotrisiloxane	D3	C ₆ H ₁₈ O ₃ Si ₃
Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane	D4	C ₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ Si ₄
Decamethylcyclopentasiloxane	D5	C ₁₀ H ₃₀ O ₅ Si ₅

3. Materials and methods

2.1 Primary gas standards

Seven Primary gas standards (PSMs) containing siloxanes in methane were prepared gravimetrically in high-pressure cylinders according to ISO 6142-1 [2-4] (Table 2).

Table 2: Gravimetric composition including expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) in $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ of the seven PSMs

	L2	U(L2)	L3	U(L3)	D3	U(D3)	D4	U(D4)	D5	U(D5)
VSL347730	0.299350	0.000043	0.201890	0.000034	0.207950	0.000396	0.063968	0.000095	0.043649	0.000078
PRM135744	0.900570	0.000213	0.795740	0.000178	0.597690	0.000151	0.575190	0.000126	0.400570	0.000100
VSL600656	3.001200	0.000415	1.995200	0.000200	1.990000	0.000205	0.596920	0.000150	0.420510	0.000217
VSL805228	3.002900	0.000610	2.014800	0.000409	1.998900	0.000429	0.594450	0.000114	0.435100	0.000076
VSL244858	3.003900	0.000456	2.006900	0.000305	1.993200	0.000335	0.803120	0.000307	0.394960	0.000246
VSL244251	3.977800	0.001249	2.501800	0.000807	1.601100	0.000576	0.575190	0.000126	0.400570	0.000100
VSL145000	4.000100	0.001279	2.515800	0.000826	1.610130	0.000587	0.807620	0.000313	0.397170	0.000248

2.2 GC-FID

The analysis were performed on a gas chromatograph with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID) with gas autosampler and a pressure controlling device. The settings used for the analytical method are listed in Table 3. The GC column, the liners, tubing and reducers were all passivated.

Table 3: GC method

Method parameter	GC-FID
Instrument	Agilent 7820A GC with FID

Column	DB-1MS-UI, 60 m long, 0.25 mm internal diameter, 0.25 μm film thickness
Injection	Via split spitless inlet with a split ratio of 3:1 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 1 mL sample volume
Oven settings	5 min 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ 5 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to 140 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ hold time 1 min 35 $^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ to 185 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ hold time 2.3 min
Detector settings	250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ H ₂ flow rate 30 mL min ⁻¹ Air flow rate 350 mL min ⁻¹ Make up N ₂ flow rate 25 mL min ⁻¹
Sample loop	70 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ sample gas flow 25 μL directly injected to the column

4. Validation

3.1 General procedure overview

The general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument is summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Overview of the performance evaluation process for determination of the performance characteristics.

Step	Phase	Description	Results
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	Siloxanes, the validation was done with L2, L3, D3, D4 and D5.
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	See Table 2
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	See Table 2
5	Experimental	Perform a multi-point calibration experiment by collecting instrument response data for measurements of the reference gas mixtures specified in step 4. The entire experiment should be conducted within a time period equivalent to that between routine calibrations.	Two multi-point calibrations were performed. The first one on 28-08-2024 and the second on 02-09-2024. VSL347730 was not analysed during the first

			measurement on 28-08-2024.
6	Calculation	Calculate the calibration functions and analysis functions for each specified component using regression analysis and validate the compatibility of the functions with the calibration data set.	See section 3.3
7	Calculation	Calculate instrumental errors and uncertainties for each component over a specified range of compositions using the functions and reference data collated in steps 5 and 6.	See section 3.4
8	Calculation	From the distribution of errors and the unbiased uncertainty estimates calculated in step 7, determine the mean error and its uncertainty for each measurand.	See section 3.6

3.2 Limit of detection and quantification

The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for the different siloxanes was calculated based on the replicate measurement of the lowest amount fraction analysed (Table 5) according to equation (1).

$$s'_0 = \frac{s_0}{\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{equation (1)}$$

Where:

- s'_0 the standard deviation used for calculating LOD and LOQ
- s_0 is the estimated standard deviation of 8 single results at or low amount fraction
- n is 8, the number of replicate observations averaged when reporting results where each replicate is obtained following the measurement procedure
- n_b is the number of blank observations used to calculate the blank correction.

Then LOD and LOQ are calculated as follows:

$$\text{LOD} = 3 \times s'_0$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times s'_0$$

Table 5: Calculated limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) for siloxanes in nmol mol⁻¹.

Siloxane	Target amount fraction μmol mol ⁻¹	s'_0 μmol mol ⁻¹	LOD μmol mol ⁻¹	LOQ μmol mol ⁻¹

			$(s'_0 = 3)$	$(s'_0 = 10)$
L2	0.30	0.00052	0.0016	0.0052
L3	0.20	0.00041	0.0012	0.0041
D3	0.21	0.00068	0.0020	0.0068
D4	0.064	0.00048	0.0015	0.0048
D5	0.044	0.00040	0.0012	0.0040

3.3 Working range and linearity

The linearity of the GC-FID has been tested for each siloxane in different ranges (Table 6). The linearity assessment was performed according to ISO 6143 [5]. For a satisfactory fit of the data, it was required that the absolute value of the normalized residual was not exceeding 2. The normalized residual is the residual divided by the standard uncertainty.

Table 6: Siloxane measurement ranges

Siloxane	Measurement range on 28-08-2024 ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	Measurement range on 02-09-2024 ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)
L2	0.90 – 4.00	0.30 – 4.00
L3	0.79 – 2.52	0.20 – 2.52
D3	0.60 – 2.00	0.21 – 2.00
D4	0.30 – 0.81	0.06 – 0.81
D5	0.30 – 0.44	0.04 – 0.44

For the linearity test, the function used is a straight line ($y = ax + b$). All the normalized residuals were < 2 , indicating this function is fit for purpose for all siloxanes under test (Figure 1-5).

Figure 1: Linear regression function and residuals for siloxane L2 on the left for the first measurement and on the right for the second measurement

Figure 2: Linear regression function and residuals for siloxane L3 on the left for the first measurement and on the right for the second measurement

Figure 3: Linear regression function and residuals for siloxane D3 on the left for the first measurement and on the right for the second measurement

Figure 4: Linear regression function and residuals for siloxane D4 on the left for the first measurement and on the right for the second measurement

Figure 5: Linear regression function and residuals for siloxane D5 on the left for the first measurement and on the right for the second measurement

3.4 Trueness, Bias

The trueness or bias was determined by calculating the bias and relative bias of the mean response compared to the linear regression function (Table 7-11).

Table 7: Calculated bias for siloxane L2

Mixture	Measurement 28-08-2024		Measurement 02-09-2024	
	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)
VSL347730	-0.00207	-0.07	0.004178	0.05
PRM135744	0.02659	0.32	-0.099555	-0.36
VSL600656	-0.10696	-0.39	-0.093898	-0.34
VSL805228	-0.10132	-0.37	0.046251	0.17
VSL244858	0.038812	0.14	0.122375	0.34
VSL244251	0.101127	0.28	0.051566	0.14
VSL145000	0.030002	0.08	0.004178	0.05

Table 8: Calculated bias for siloxane L3

Mixture	Measurement 28-08-2024		Measurement 02-09-2024	
	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)
VSL347730	0.005727	0.23	-0.028486	-0.28
PRM135744	-0.15915	-1.55	0.40841	1.64
VSL600656	0.440399	1.77	0.150052	0.59
VSL805228	0.184689	0.73	0.013691	0.05
VSL244858	0.047263	0.19	-0.292799	-0.92
VSL244251	-0.19218	-0.6	-0.368524	-1.14
VSL145000	-0.26601	-0.82	-0.028486	-0.28

Table 9: Calculated bias for siloxane D3

Mixture	Measurement 28-08-2024		Measurement 02-09-2024	
	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)
VSL347730	0.008652	0.45	0.015524	0.27
PRM135744	-0.08816	-1.51	0.076385	0.4
VSL600656	0.14274	0.74	0.053555	0.28
VSL805228	0.120972	0.62	0.304294	1.6
VSL244858	0.371025	1.95	-0.175418	-1.11
VSL244251	-0.15659	-0.99	-0.235892	-1.48
VSL145000	-0.21596	-1.36	0.015524	0.27

Table 10: Calculated bias for siloxane D4

Mixture	Measurement 28-08-2024		Measurement 02-09-2024	
	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)
VSL347730	-0.00082	-0.08	-0.006965	-0.17
PRM135744	0.015492	0.37	-0.072947	-0.92
VSL600656	-0.07386	-0.93	0.03661	0.45
VSL805228	0.033826	0.42	0.106105	1.32
VSL244858	0.103535	1.29	-0.050656	-0.46
VSL244251	-0.07122	-0.65	-0.028675	-0.26
VSL145000	-0.04963	-0.45	-0.006965	-0.17

Table 11: Calculated bias for siloxane D5

Mixture	Measurement 28-08-2024		Measurement 02-09-2024	
	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)	Bias (a.u.)	Bias (%)
VSL347730	0.000656	0.08	0.00228	0.04
PRM135744	-0.09803	-1.79	0.099576	1.42
VSL600656	0.114304	1.63	-0.045058	-0.6
VSL805228	-0.00704	-0.09	0.026441	0.35
VSL244858	0.081616	1.07	-0.04512	-0.64
VSL244251	-0.03696	-0.52	-0.042529	-0.6
VSL145000	-0.03179	-0.45	0.00228	0.04

The bias for L2 ranges from -0.39% to 0.34%. The bias for L3 ranges from -1.55% to 1.77%. The bias for D3 ranges from -1.51% to 1.95%. The bias for D4 ranges from -0.93% to 1.32% and the bias for D5 ranges from -1.79% to 1.63%.

3.5 Precision

To determine the precision of the measurement results obtained with the analyser the repeatability and reproducibility standard deviations have been determined from the response factors (RF). The RF is calculated by dividing the response by the amount fraction. The repeatability standard deviation ($s(r)$, %) and reproducibility standard deviation ($s(R)$, %)

were calculated according to ISO 5725-2:2019 using analysis of variance (ANOVA) [6] (Table 12).

Table 12: Repeatability standard deviation ($s(r)$, %) and reproducibility standard deviation ($s(R)$, %) for siloxane L2

Siloxane	$s(r)$, %	$s(R)$, %
L2	0.27	0.51
L3	0.30	1.54
D3	0.39	1.90
D4	0.61	1.56
D5	1.62	2.89

3.6 Measurement uncertainties

To calculate the measurement uncertainty the following uncertainty sources were taken into account (Table 13):

- The uncertainty of the reference standard (u_{ref})
- The bias (Δ)
- The precision ($s(R)$)

The relative expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$) were calculated using the law of propagation of uncertainty according to the GUM [7].

Table 13: Relative measurement uncertainty of the GC-FID for siloxanes

Siloxane	u_{ref} , %	Δ , %	$s(R)$, %	$u(k = 1)$	$U(k = 2)$
L2	2.0	0.4	0.5	2.1	4
L3	2.0	1.8	1.5	3.1	6
D3	3.0	2.0	1.9	4.1	8
D4	3.0	1.3	1.6	3.6	7
D5	4.0	1.8	2.9	5.3	11

A measurement uncertainty of 10% or less is considered reliable. The calculation show that the measurement uncertainties are below 10% save for D5 which has a measurement uncertainty of 11%. The high measurement reproducibility could be caused by the by the low vapour pressure of siloxane D5, as a result of which handling of the reference materials and samples becomes a critical point.

5. Conclusions

The validation of the GC-FID method to analyse siloxanes L2, L3, D3, D4 and D5 was performed according to the performance assessment protocol [1].

The GC-FID method was found to be fit-for-purpose, reliable and highly sensitive. The LOD and LOQ are a few nmol mol⁻¹. Linear functions for all siloxanes were obtained with a straight line, with a bias smaller than 2%. The precision was also below 2% save for siloxane D5 which had a reproducibility standard deviation of 2.9%. Finally leading to a relative expanded measurement uncertainty below 10% for all siloxanes save for D5 which has a relative expanded measurement uncertainty of 11%.

6. References

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REPORT

A.2.2.1: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for siloxanes with TD-GC/MS/FID using the static standards produced in A1.1.2.

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7. Introduction

The BiometCAP project is developing a performance assessment protocol (A2.1.4) for evaluating instruments and methods used for biomethane conformity assessment. Here, this performance assessment protocol was tested and validated using the method ISO 2620:2024 for the determination of Disiloxane hexamethyl (L2), Trisiloxane octamethyl (L3), Cyclotrisiloxane hexamethyl (D3), Cyclotetrasiloxane octamethyl (D4) and Cyclopentasiloxane decamethyl (D5) in biogas/biomethane matrices. The method is based on thermal desorption followed by gas chromatography with a mass spectrometer and a flame ionization detector (TD-GC/MS-FID). The validation parameters evaluated here were selectivity, limit of detection and quantification, working range and linearity, trueness/bias, and precision. Using these results, the measurement uncertainty was calculated for each component.

8. Materials and methods

The TD-GC/MS-FID instrument was operated in electron impact mode with standard conditions, including an electron energy of 70 eV and a mass scan range from 29 to 300 amu. The analysis utilized a BPX5 column measuring 50 m x 32 mm ID x 1 µm with 5% phenylpolysilphenylene siloxane. Sorbent tubes underwent a two-step thermal desorption process using a Markes TD100 desorber by first heating the tubes to 275 °C for seven minutes to release the adsorbed species. These substances were then focused at -10 °C in a cold trap containing graphitized carbon before being rapidly heated to 300 °C for separation on the GC column. The column effluent was split for detection and quantification, with one stream passing through a flame ionization detector (FID) and the other through a mass spectrometer (MS).

A reference mixture produced by NPL in methane as part of activity A1.1.2 containing 0.0874 ± 0.0044 µmol/mol of L2, 0.0557 ± 0.0034 µmol/mol of L3, 0.0542 ± 0.0038 µmol/mol of D3, 0.0429 ± 0.0026 µmol/mol of D4 and 0.0326 ± 0.002 µmol/mol of D5 was used for the validation.

9. Validation

General overview

The planning steps of the general procedure for determining the performance characteristics of the instrument taken from the protocol developed in A2.1.4 are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Four steps with general procedure for determination of the performance characteristics.

Step	Phase	Description	Results
1	Planning	Specify the components required to be measured by the instrument and the measurement range for each over which the instrument shall be evaluated.	Validation will be done for L2, L3, D3, D4 and D5
2	Planning	Establish the functional descriptions of the response functions assumed by the instrument for each specified component.	The response should be linear.
3	Planning	Specify a set of reference gas mixtures (calibration gases) with compositions covering all ranges for all components specified in step 1.	Only one gas mixture will be used: NPL mixture prepared as part of A1.1.2. for bias. A reference solution of all the siloxanes in diethylether was used for the calibration.
4	Planning	Establish the composition and uncertainty of the calibration gas mixture(s) to be used for routine calibration of the instrument.	Around 0.06 ± 0.004 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ per compound

The extent of the performance characteristic validation taken from the protocol designed in A2.1.4 is summarised for this application in Table 2.

Table 2. Extent of validation.

Performance characteristic	Analytical application		
	Component identification	Component detection	Component quantification
Selectivity	x	x	x
Limit of detection		x	
Limit of quantification			x
Working range			x
Trueness			x
Precision			x
Rise time			Not applicable
Memory effect and fall time			Not applicable

Based on previous experiences, for this method, the targeted relative within-laboratory reproducibility, $u(R_w)$, is set at 2.5 % and the targeted relative bias, $u(\text{bias})$, is set at 5%.

Selectivity

Protocol: To perform the selectivity evaluation, use a reference material containing both the analyte of interest and other components that are expected to be present within the biomethane samples.

Here we used a reference biogas sample containing both the analyte of interest and other components. The selectivity of the method was investigated by studying its ability to measure the analyte of interest in the sample where interferences have been introduced. The method should be optimized to avoid co-elution of the analyte of interest and the other components present in the sample. With the selected GC parameters for this method and with an FID detector, the following chromatogram was obtained for a biogas sample from a plant digesting food waste (figure 1). As can be seen in the figure, D4 elutes close to a dimethyloctene (probably 2-Octene, 3,7-dimethyl).

Figure 1. The TD-GC using FID detector shows that D4 eluates close to a dimethyl-octene.

Resolution was calculated according to this equation [1]:

$$\frac{t_{R2} - t_{R1}}{\frac{1}{2}(W_1 + W_2)}$$

Where t_{R2} , t_{R1} are retention time for each peak and W_1 , W_2 are width of each peak. A resolution of 1.5 or more occurs when the signal returns to its baseline between two peaks, indicating good separation. D4 eluate close to a dimethyl-octene and calculation of the peak resolution gives a value of 1.2, indicating a slight overlap between peaks and poor resolution.

The same sample with an MS detector provides a good resolution of the chromatogram and no co-elution of D4 with other compounds, see figure 2.

Figure 2. The TD-GC using MS detector shows good resolution of D4.

Limit of detection and quantification

Protocol: the LOD and LOQ are calculated in one of two ways: via replicate measurements of blank samples, or via replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte.

In this case, the method “replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte” was chosen. The limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ) for L2, L3, D3, D4 and D5 were calculated with a Signal-to-Noise (S/N) approach. The S/N ratio is determined by comparing signals from samples with known low amount of analyte with those of blank samples. LOD and LOQ is the determination of the minimum amount at which the analyte can be confidently detected and quantified. Here, the LOD is determined for S/N = 3 and the LOQ for S/N = 10. The results are presented in Table 3. The results show that the method is highly sensitive and can be used to analyze samples with low amount fractions of siloxanes.

Table 3. Calculated limits of detection and quantification for siloxanes.

Compounds	Target amount ng	Noise	Signal	S/N at target amount	LOD ng (S/N = 3)	LOQ ng (S/N = 10)
L2 MS	2.9	200	9600	48	0.18	0.61
L3 MS	2.7	700	6440	9.2	0.89	2.96
D3 MS	2.5	1150	37000	32	0.23	0.77
D4 MS	2.6	1100	29550	27	0.29	0.98
D5 MS	2.5	1300	11050	8.5	0.88	2.94
L2 FID	2.9	120	1550	13	0.68	2.26
L3 FID	2.7	190	1725	9	0.90	3.00
D3 FID	2.5	181	5820	32	0.23	0.77
D4 FID	2.6	200	4700	23.5	0.34	1.12
D5 FID	2.5	168	3350	20	0.38	1.25

Working range and linearity

Protocol: To assess the instrument working range:

- 1) Identify the **range of interest** (recommended to span $\pm 10\%$ of the expected calibration range) and measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across this range.
- 2) Plot response against amount fraction and visually examine plot to identify the approximate **linear range**.
- 3) To quantify linearity over the identified **linear range**, measure blanks and calibration standards at 6 - 10 amount fractions spread evenly across the linear range.
- 4) Plot response (y axis) against amount fraction (x axis) and calculate appropriate regression statistics. Plot the residuals (difference in observed y value and predicted by the straight line fit). Random distribution around zero confirms linearity.

L2

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts (nanograms,ng) of L2. Results for L2 measured in the range 3 to 117 ng are shown in Figure 3. As illustrated in Figure 3, the correlation coefficient for L2 measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 3 to 117 ng.

Figure 3. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 4).

Figure 4. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

L3

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of L3. Results for L3 measured in the range 3 to 109 ng are shown in Figure 5. As illustrated in Figure 5, the correlation coefficient for L3 measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 3 to 109 ng.

Figure 5. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residual is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 6).

Figure 6. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

D3

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of D3. Results for D3 measured in the range 3 to 100 ng are shown in Figure 7. As illustrated in Figure 7, the correlation coefficient for D3 measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 3 to 100 ng.

Figure 7. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residual is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 8).

Figure 8. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

D4

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of D4. Results for D4 measured in the range 3 to 105 ng are shown in Figure 9. As illustrated in Figure 9, the correlation coefficient for D4 measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 3 to 105 ng.

Figure 9. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 10).

Figure 10. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

D5

The linearity was assessed by analyzing seven different amounts in nanograms (ng) of D5. Results for D5 measured in the range 3 to 100 ng are shown in Figure 11. As illustrated in Figure 11, the correlation coefficient for D5 measured with GC-MS/FID is close to a value of 1.00, suggesting that the equation for the linear regression fits the data. This observation implies that the method encompasses a linear working range within 3 to 100 ng.

Figure 11. Correlation between the area measured with MS or FID detector and the known amount of sample in ng.

The distribution of residuals is random, confirming the linearity and working range (figure 12).

Figure 12. The residual of the difference between calculated area and measured area in GC-MS/FID plotted against known amount of sample in ng.

Trueness, Bias

Protocol, approach 1: evaluation against a reference material: compare mean measured value, with the reference value for the reference material. Calculate bias, relative bias, or the relative recovery (apparent recovery)

The differences between the calculated concentrations and the expected concentrations are presented in Table 4. Using this result, the standard deviation of the measured concentration, S_{RW} , was calculated to be 1.8 %. Taking into account the uncertainty of the reference standard, the total bias, $u(\text{bias})$, was calculated to be 4.56% which is in good agreement with the targeted value of 5%.

Table 4. Bias calculated for L2 with MS.

Results $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Expected results, $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$	Bias	Relative Bias
557	585	-28	-5
561	585	-24	-4
579	585	-6	-1
581	585	-4	-1
542	585	-43	-7
	Mean	-21	-3.6

Precision

Protocol: To evaluate repeatability, measure the analyte(s) of interest within a reference material at various concentrations spread across the working range using the same method. Obtain at least 10 replicate measurements and calculate the standard deviation and relative standard deviation.

Precision was assessed by measuring 10-12 duplicates of L2, L3, D3, D4 and D5 at varying quantities using TD-GC-MS/FID on several days. Standard deviation, as well as relative standard deviation, were determined and the pooled standard deviation was calculated. The results are presented in Table 5-12.

Table 5. Estimation of the intermediate precision for L2 using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	7.02	7.34	0.23	3.17
2 (240205)	22.21	22.10	0.08	0.36
3 (240205)	29.46	29.26	0.14	0.47
4 (240207)	2.43	2.52	0.07	2.71
5 (240207)	5.70	5.57	0.09	1.63
6 (240207)	8.60	8.41	0.13	1.57
7 (240207)	11.72	11.84	0.09	0.73
8 (240209)	4.29	4.29	0.01	0.13
9(240209)	8.74	8.82	0.06	0.67
10(240209)	13.08	13.23	0.11	0.80
11(240209)	17.60	17.65	0.04	0.22
12(240219)	10.77	10.50	0.19	1.79
			Rel STD	1.5 %
			Sr % pooled	1.5 %

Table 6. Estimation of the intermediate precision for L2 using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	19.6	21.1	1.11	5.43
2 (240205)	60.2	63.2	2.14	3.46

3 (240205)	85.2	82.8	1.71	2.03
4 (240207)	8.9	8.7	0.19	2.15
5 (240207)	18.7	17.6	0.73	4.01
6 (240207)	26.0	24.7	0.96	3.80
7 (240207)	34.4	36.6	1.56	4.40
8 (240209)	14.5	13.7	0.57	4.06
9(240209)	26.3	26.3	0.01	0.04
10(240209)	38.4	37.6	0.57	1.50
11(240209)	49.3	48.6	0.46	0.94
12(240219)	27.8	27.9	0.09	0.32
			Rel STD	3.3%
			Sr % pooled	3.1%

Table 7. Estimation of the intermediate precision for L3 using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	6.81	6.83	0.01	0.21
2 (240205)	20.50	20.32	0.13	0.64
3 (240205)	26.96	26.96	0.00	0.00
4 (240207)	2.30	2.31	0.01	0.39
5 (240207)	5.20	5.25	0.04	0.67
6 (240207)	7.95	7.84	0.08	1.02
7 (240207)	13.32	13.29	0.02	0.12
8 (240209)	4.12	4.02	0.07	1.73
9 (240209)	8.27	8.18	0.06	0.76
10(240209)	12.22	12.37	0.10	0.82
11(240209)	16.50	16.41	0.06	0.39
12(240219)	9.73	9.62	0.08	0.79
			Rel STD	0.8%
			Sr % pooled	0.8%

Table 8. Estimation of the intermediate precision for L3 using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	8.89	9.12	0.16	1.81

2 (240205)	27.33	28.70	0.97	3.46
3 (240205)	38.88	37.95	0.66	1.72
4 (240207)	4.23	3.92	0.22	5.38
5 (240207)	8.60	7.75	0.60	7.39
6 (240207)	11.74	11.00	0.52	4.60
7 (240209)	19.91	18.70	0.85	4.41
8 (240209)	6.30	5.96	0.24	3.85
9 (240209)	11.77	11.70	0.05	0.43
10(240209)	17.55	17.10	0.32	1.84
11(240219)	22.63	22.56	0.05	0.23
12(240219)	11.91	12.42	0.36	2.96
			Rel STD	4.0%
			Sr % pooled	3.8%

Table 9. Estimation of the intermediate precision for D4 using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	6.26	6.26	0.00	0.04
2 (240205)	17.45	17.15	0.21	1.23
3 (240205)	22.31	23.15	0.59	2.60
4 (240207)	4.78	5.42	0.45	8.88
5 (240207)	7.07	6.88	0.13	1.89
6 (240207)	10.18	10.33	0.11	1.04
7 (240207)	12.44	13.67	0.87	6.64
8 (240209)	10.21	10.14	0.05	0.47
9 (240209)	14.06	13.66	0.28	2.00
10(240219)	6.24	5.93	0.21	3.50
			Rel STD	3.6%
			Sr % pooled	3.9%

Table 10. Estimation of the intermediate precision for D4 using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	11.73	10.85	0.62	5.50
2 (240205)	30.67	31.53	0.61	1.95

3 (240205)	41.94	42.73	0.56	1.32
4 (240207)	10.32	10.75	0.31	2.93
5 (240207)	13.49	12.98	0.36	2.70
6 (240207)	19.00	21.20	1.56	7.76
7 (240207)	24.69	26.02	0.94	3.70
8(240209)	19.36	18.45	0.65	3.42
9(240209)	25.78	24.77	0.71	2.81
10(240219)	11.39	11.13	0.18	1.64
			Rel STD	4.2%
			Sr % pooled	3.8%

Table 11. Estimation of the intermediate precision for D5 using GC-FID.

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	5.40	5.29	0.08	1.47
2 (240205)	15.37	15.12	0.18	1.16
3 (240205)	19.72	20.34	0.43	2.17
4 (240207)	4.01	4.30	0.21	4.99
5 (240207)	5.98	5.82	0.11	1.92
6 (240207)	8.37	8.31	0.04	0.49
7 (240207)	10.13	10.88	0.53	5.07
8 (240209)	6.03	5.85	0.13	2.16
9 (240209)	8.89	8.80	0.06	0.73
10(240209)	12.03	11.67	0.25	2.12
11(240219)	8.00	7.37	0.45	5.82
12(240219)	5.42	5.07	0.25	4.70
			Rel STD	3.4%
			Sr % pooled	3.3%

Table 12. Estimation of the intermediate precision for D5 using GC-MS

Replicates	Meas. 1 (ng)	Meas. 2 (ng)	S	CV
1 (240205)	5.75	5.38	0.26	4.64
2 (240205)	15.54	16.10	0.39	2.47
3 (240205)	22.26	22.47	0.15	0.66

4 (240207)	4.87	4.78	0.06	1.23
5 (240207)	6.19	6.10	0.06	0.95
6 (240207)	8.40	8.88	0.34	3.95
7 (240207)	10.55	10.65	0.08	0.72
8 (240209)	6.38	6.06	0.23	3.63
9 (240209)	9.04	8.87	0.12	1.32
10(240209)	12.08	11.63	0.32	2.69
11(240219)	7.74	7.51	0.16	2.10
12(240219)	5.73	5.83	0.07	1.14
			Rel STD	2.7
			Sr % pooled	2.5

The measured Sr varies between 0.8 to 3.9 %. Taking into account, the contribution of control samples (here toluene), the within-laboratory reproducibility, $u(R_w)$, is evaluated to be 3.04% for L2 in MS, a bit higher than the targeted value of 2.5%.

Measurement uncertainties

The expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) for L2 was calculated using the software MUKit. In general for a GC method, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered acceptable and the method reliable. The calculations show that the measurement uncertainty is 11% which is slightly above the limit for reliable methods (Table 13).

Table 13. Within-laboratory reproducibility, method biases and expanded uncertainties from the TD-GC-MS/FID system for siloxanes.

Compounds	$u(R_w)$ rel.	$u(\text{bias})$ rel.	$U = 2u_c$
L2	3.04%	4.56%	11%

10. Conclusions

The validation of the method ISO 2620:2024 for siloxanes was performed according to the performance assessment protocol written in (A2.1.4). However, only two CRM were used compared to three recommended in the protocol for a linear regression, but the method had previously been validated using five different CRM.

ISO 2620:2024 is therefore found to be fit-for-purpose, reliable and highly sensitive. As the working range is at least 2 to 100 ng, it can be used to analyze samples with amount fractions of siloxanes from 2 nmol/mol to 1 μ mol/mol (using volumes of 5 to 200 ml per tube).

11. References

[1] Shimadzu, <https://www.shimadzu.com/an/service-support/technical-support/analysis-basics/basic/resol-1>.